

ISic1269

I.Sicily inscription 1269

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble ('bardiglio')

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico, inventory 43

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140758

1. ἐνθάδε κίτε □
2. Ἀγάθων πιστὸς
3. ζήσας ἔτη ζ, μήνας
4. ζ· ἀνεπαύσατο
5. ὑπατ (ία) Ὀνωρίου τὸ η
6. κὲ Θεοδοσίου τὸ γ' Σε-
7. β (αστῶν) □ Ααυύγγ (ούστων) ²⁶Αύγούστων δυοῖν²⁶ τῆ πρὸ γ' #⁵⁶
8. εἰδῶν Ὀκτωβρίων
9. ἡμέρα Σελήνης. □
- 10.

Edition: PHI331433

1. . . . Σε-
2. β (αστῶν) □ Ααυύγγ (ούστων) ²⁶Αύγούστων δυοῖν²⁶ τῆ πρὸ γ' {²⁷[ε']²⁷} #⁵⁶
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492876

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Bibliography

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